

KEY FEATURES OF LEARNINGAPPS IN IMPROVING THE KNOWLEDGE OF MEDICAL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Training is based on the use of modern technical means, i.e. computers and the Internet during the medical course. Using the possibilities of creating interactive games in mathematics to improve the quality of education. The object of our research work is future teachers educating schoolchildren.

Introduction: Currently, the development of information technology is developing so rapidly that yesterday's technologies are already outdated, and new ones are replacing them. This, in turn, may become a kind of obsolete technology the day after tomorrow. It was emphasized that it was necessary to increase the interest of young people in the natural sciences, divide talented students into small groups and organize them in specialized schools, and then in higher educational institutions. The goal was to create popular textbooks and teaching aids for schoolchildren on this subject, written in simple and understandable language, to develop their ability to think, if necessary, from kindergarten.

Literature review and methodology. There are many online resources for creating interactive exercises. They may be similar in functionality and may differ in functionality and interface. Some services can be learned very quickly, while others require a lot of work to learn how to work with them. But one way or another, each of them is unique, interesting and useful. With one service we can create a quick and effective quiz. Another service helps us create crosswords. And that's great. But still, probably, each of us would like to have a tool for creating teaching materials that will help us in any situation, and we can call it UNIVERSAL. It's amazing that such a tool exists! The interactive assignment designer LearningApps is designed to support the learning process using interactive modules (exercises). Both the teacher and the student can create interactive modules based on ready-made templates. LearningApps is a Web 2.0 application developed as part of a research project at the Bern College of Teacher Education and Computer Science at the University of Mainz and the University of Zittau/Görlitz (Germany). The main idea of interactive tasks that can be created thanks to this service is that

students can test and consolidate their knowledge in a playful way, which will improve their cognitive abilities (perception, imagination, analysis of work), and contribute to the formation of interests.

The main idea of interactive tasks that can be created thanks to this service is that students can test and consolidate their knowledge in a playful way, which helps to develop their cognitive interest in a particular academic subject.

Service address - <http://learningApps.org/>

The service has a conceptual user interface, offers registration (buttons "Login" - "Create a new account") and is available in 20 languages, including Russian and Belarusian. To select the desired language, select the icon with the corresponding flag in the upper right corner of the site page. The site has a public gallery of interactive tasks created by users of the resource. All exercises presented in the service are divided by topic, which makes it much easier to find the task you need. It is very easy to understand the functionality and navigation of the service. To do this, simply click the "All Exercises" button at the top of the main page and you will see a list of exercises created and published by other users. You need to register to create and save your tasks on the site. Once you complete the registration process, you will be provided with templates to help you create an interactive activity. Templates of the proposed exercises are grouped by functional characteristics. Once you create a task, you can publish it immediately or save it for personal use. Access to ready-made resources is also open to unregistered users. You can use tasks created by colleagues by copying the link at the bottom of the task from the Link field and pasting it into a page on your personal site. Works created in this service can be published on the pages of a personal website (blog), "shared" on social networks, and also sent a link to them by email to colleagues and students.

You can also create accounts for your students and test their knowledge from your own resources right on this site.

In the upper left corner of the site's home page, you can see a section called "What is LearningApps.org?" there are links to sections, and by clicking the "Show help" button, you will be taken to the site pages, where you can familiarize yourself with basic information about the service and visit the "Tutor's Account", where the most important functions of this service are explained.

This service is universal for many reasons:

Firstly, it has a very simple and user-friendly interface.

Secondly, it gives you the opportunity to work in a language that is convenient for you.

Thirdly, in this service you can create all kinds of interactive exercises without anyone's invitation. All tips and exercises are included in templates.

Fourth, before creating a new exercise, you can read the example and immediately see the end result.

Fifthly, even without registration, you can use exercises already created by your colleagues, because they are in the public domain.

Sixthly, the service has a very "Soft" beautiful design. It attracts users with its "Appearance" and will not disappoint them in the future.

Seventh, there are not many services on the Internet that allow you to create teaching materials in your native language. But LearningApps Interactive Task Builder is an exception because it not only allows you to create exercises in your native language, but also allows you to work with its interface.

This online resource has practically no disadvantages. In addition, you can probably only work with it online.

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